

Appendix to Individualism, institutions and patriarchal attitudes
Appendix A: Summary statistics

Variables	# observations	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
<i>Patriarchal attitudes</i>					
Patriarchal attitudes index (PAI)	93	0.01	1.60	-2.92	3.39
Men right to job	93	0.37	0.20	0.03	0.88
Men better leaders	93	0.45	0.22	0.05	0.86
University for boy	93	0.23	0.13	0.01	0.62
<i>Individualism measures</i>					
Individualism	93	3.72	1.47	1.33	8.08
Gov ownership	93	5.32	0.74	3.49	6.75
Make parents proud	93	0.83	0.16	0.31	1.00
Justifiable: homosexuality	93	3.09	1.61	1.01	7.50
Gov responsibility	93	5.93	0.87	4.04	7.70
Individualism BMH	93	-0.13	1.69	-2.35	5.00
Individualism Hofstede	62	42.94	23.49	6.00	91.00
Schwartz index	42	0.08	0.78	-1.25	1.74
<i>Control variables</i>					
Oil (% GDP)	93	2.58	6.85	0.00	40.23
Latitude	93	33.17	16.94	0.23	64.15
Landlocked	93	0.20	0.41	0.00	1.00
Common law	93	0.24	0.43	0.00	1.00
GDP per capita (log)	88	9.77	1.00	7.33	11.55
Exports (% GDP)	88	41.21	28.87	7.94	177.65
Services (% GDP)	88	57.36	9.95	33.50	90.01
Manufacturing (% GDP)	88	13.41	5.31	1.03	26.77
Agriculture (% GDP)	88	7.46	7.45	0.03	36.78
Female schooling	82	9.16	2.57	2.09	13.23
Female LFP	82	50.95	15.14	11.53	83.89
Fertility	82	2.09	0.94	0.92	5.89
Plough	89	0.68	0.44	0.00	1.00
Agricultural revolution	89	5.89	1.97	1.48	10.38
Catholic	91	0.28	0.34	0.00	0.94
Protestant	91	0.13	0.21	0.00	0.90
Other Christian	91	0.07	0.10	0.00	0.45
Orthodox	91	0.09	0.20	0.00	0.92
Jewish	91	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02
Muslim	91	0.24	0.35	0.00	0.99
Hindu	91	0.02	0.08	0.00	0.77
Buddhism	91	0.03	0.12	0.00	0.85
Communism	93	0.08	0.27	0.00	1.00
Gender_noun	49	0.98	0.99	0.00	2.00
Gender_pronoun	49	1.06	0.83	0.00	2.00
Political ideology	89	5.71	0.70	2.71	9.07
Hofstede masculinity	51	51.20	20.22	5.00	110.00
Hofstede power distance	51	58.61	21.60	11.00	104.00
Hofstede uncertainty avoidance	51	65.04	23.09	8.00	112.00

Trust	83	0.26	0.16	0.04	0.68
Religious attendance	83	4.33	1.31	1.82	6.65
Climate	75	0.70	0.31	0.02	1.00
Soil	75	0.61	0.20	0.20	0.96
<i>Formal institutions</i>					
Liberal democracy	92	-0.99	0.77	-3.15	-0.12
Economic freedom	91	1.97	0.12	1.60	2.19
Rule of law	93	0.20	0.99	-1.85	2.02
Control corruption	93	0.15	1.03	-1.60	2.17
WBL index	93	4.36	0.25	3.38	4.61
WPR index	90	0.73	0.25	0.00	1.10
<i>Instruments</i>					
Historical disease	83	0.02	0.65	-1.31	1.16
Ancestral rainfall variation	83	-0.18	0.43	-0.69	0.94
Pronoun drop	73	0.71	0.45	0.00	1.00
LIFE	73	6.81	1.22	5.17	11.62

Notes: Summary statistics are based on the un-standardized version of the data.

Appendix B: Data description

Variables	Definition and Source
<u>Patriarchal attitudes</u>	
Men right to job	Based on IVS question and coded as share of respondents in a country who agree that “When jobs are scarce, men should have more right to a job than women”. Data collected from Integrated Values Survey, Haerpfer et al. (2021). Individual answers are averaged across respondents to aggregate by country and then averaged across all waves. Data are standardized.
Men better leaders	Based on IVS question and coded as share of respondents in a country who agree or strongly agree that “On the whole, men make better political leaders than women do”. Data collected from Integrated Values Survey, Haerpfer et al. (2021). Individual answers are averaged across respondents to aggregate by country and then averaged across all waves. Data are standardized.
University for boy	Based on IVS question and coded as share of respondents in a country who agree or strongly agree that “A university education is more important for a boy than for a girl”. Data collected from Integrated Values Survey, Haerpfer et al. (2021). Individual answers are averaged across respondents to aggregate by country and then averaged across all waves. Data are standardized.
Patriarchal attitudes index (PAI)	Index created from extracting the first principal component from the three IVS patriarchal attitudes questions. A higher score indicates more patriarchal attitudes. The index is standardized.
<u>Individualism measures</u>	
Gov ownership	Based on IVS question, coded from 1 to 10 where 10 indicates completely agree that government ownership of business and industry should be increased vs. private ownership of business and industry should be increased. Data collected from Integrated Values Survey, Haerpfer et al. (2021). Individual answers are averaged across respondents to aggregate by country and then averaged across waves. Data are standardized.
Make parents proud	Based on IVS question and coded as a share of respondents in a country who agree or strongly agree that “One of my main goals in life has been to make my parents proud”. Data collected from Integrated Values Survey, Haerpfer et al. (2021). Individual answers are averaged across respondents to aggregate by country and then averaged across waves. Data are standardized.
Justifiable: homosexuality	Based on IVS question on whether homosexuality is justifiable, coded from 1 (never justifiable) to 10 (always justifiable). Data collected from Integrated Values Survey, Haerpfer et al. (2021). Individual answers are averaged across respondents to aggregate by country and then averaged across waves. Data are standardized.
Gov responsibility	Based on a IVS question, coded from 1 to 10, where 10 indicates completely agree that government ownership of business and industry should be increased vs. private ownership of business and industry should be increased. Data collected from Integrated Values Survey, Haerpfer et al. (2021). Individual answers are averaged across respondents to aggregate by country and then averaged across waves. Data are standardized.
Individualism	Index created by extracting the first principal component from the four individualism IVS questions. A higher score reflects a greater level of individualism. Index is standardized.

Individualism BMH	Standardized index based on Beugelsdijk et al. (2015). Created by extracting the first principal component from four IVS questions: 1) Private ownership of business and industry should be increased vs. government ownership of business and industry should be increased, 2) one of main goals in life is to make parents proud, 3) whether abortion is justified, and 4) whether homosexuality is justified. A higher score reflects a greater level of individualism. Averaged across all respondents for a given country and then averaged across waves. Data collected from Integrated Values Survey, Haerpfer et al. (2021).
Individualism Hofstede	The degree to which individuals are integrated into groups; assumes weak ties among group members. Denotes the extent to which society sees people primarily as individuals looking after themselves (high individualism) or primarily as members of tightly knit communities (low individualism). Collected from Hofstede (2001). Index is standardized.
Schwartz Autonomy	An autonomy index derived from Schwartz's (2006) cultural dimension reflecting the relationship between the individual and the group. Autonomy represents independence while embeddedness emphasizes social relationships and conformity. A country level autonomy index is created by averaging affective and intellectual autonomy and then subtracting embeddedness. The index is standardized.
<u>Control variables</u>	
Oil rents	Oil rents (% of GDP). Measured in 2019. WDI (2025).
Latitude	Measured as the absolute value of the latitude of the country. Collected from CIA World Fact Book.
Landlocked	Dummy variable for whether a country is landlocked. Collected from CIA World Fact Book.
Common law	Dummy variable coded 0 or 1: 1 indicates a country has English legal tradition. La Porta et al. (2008).
GDP per capita (log)	GDP per capita, population and expenditure-side real GDP at chained purchasing-power parities in 2017 US dollars. In log form. Measured in 2019. Data are collected from Penn World Tables 10.0; Feenstra et al. (2015).
Exports (% GDP)	Exports of goods and services (% of GDP). Measured in 2019. WDI (2025).
Services (% GDP)	Services, value added (% of GDP). Measured in 2019. WDI (2025).
Manufacturing (% GDP)	Manufacturing, value added (% of GDP). Measured in 2019. WDI (2025).
Agriculture (% GDP)	Agriculture, forestry, and fishing, value added (% of GDP). Measured in 2019. WDI (2025).
Female schooling	Average years of total schooling, age 15+, female. Measured in 2010. Barro and Lee (2013).
Female LFP	Labor force participation rate, female (% of female population ages 15+) (modeled ILO estimate). Measured in 2019. World Development Indicators (2025).
Fertility	Total fertility rate (births per woman) in 2019. WDI (2025).
Plough	The share of a country's population whose ancestors used the heavy plow. Alesina et al. (2013).
Agricultural revolution	The average years elapsed since the agricultural revolution in 2000, measured in millennia, for a country's ancestors. Borcan et al. (2018), adjusted for migration in the modern era using Putterman and Weil (2010).
Religion controls	Shares of the population that are Protestant, Catholic, other Christian, Muslim, Jewish, Hindu, Buddhism, and Orthodox, in 2000. Collected from McCleary and Barro (2006).
Communism	The share of the 20 th century that a country was communist. Barro and McCleary (2003)

Gender_noun	One point is given to languages in which nouns are classified as either masculine or feminine and an additional point to languages in which the rules of gender assignment are both formal and semantic. Based on a country's dominant language. Davis and Reynolds (2018).
Gender_pronoun	An index of the gender intensity of the pronouns of a country's dominant language. The index equals zero if pronouns are not gendered, one if the third person singular is gendered and equals two if the first or second person singular is gendered (Mavisakalyan, 2015).
Political ideology	Coded from 1 to 10 to the IVS question: How would you place your views on this scale, left (1) to right (10)? Higher score represents more right leaning ideology. Data collected from Integrated Values Survey, Haerpfer et al. (2021). Individual answers are averaged across respondents to aggregate by country and then averaged across all waves.
Hofstede masculinity	Measures the extent to which a society values traditionally "masculine" traits (achievement, competitiveness, assertiveness) versus "feminine" traits (care, cooperation, quality of life). High masculinity indicates a preference for achievement and material success; low masculinity (femininity) emphasizes relationships and well-being. Higher scores represent more masculine cultures. Collected from Hofstede (2001).
Hofstede power distance	Reflects the degree to which less powerful members of a society accept and expect unequal power distribution. High power distance indicates acceptance of hierarchical authority; low power distance suggests preference for equality and participation. Higher scores reflect greater acceptance of power disparities. Collected from Hofstede (2001).
Hofstede uncertainty avoidance	Measures a society's tolerance for ambiguity and uncertainty. High uncertainty avoidance indicates a preference for structure, rules, and predictability; low uncertainty avoidance reflects comfort with ambiguity and flexibility. Higher scores indicate more uncertainty avoidance. Collected from Hofstede (2001).
Regional controls	Dummy variables reflecting a country's location in the following regions: East Asia Pacific, Eastern and Central Europe, Middle East and North Africa, South Asia, Western Europe, Sub-Saharan Africa, Latin America and the Caribbean, and North America, as defined by the World Bank, 2022.
Trust	Based on IVS question and coded as share of respondents in a country who answered yes to the question 'most people can be trusted'. Data collected from Integrated Values Survey, Haerpfer et al. (2021).
Religious attendance	Based on IVS question and coded from 1 (never) to 8 (more than once a week) to the question: How often do you attend religious services? Higher score reflects more religious service attendance. Averaged across all respondents in a country. Data collected from Integrated Values Survey, Haerpfer et al. (2021).
Climate	The suitability of a country's climate for agricultural production. Michalopoulos and Papaioannou (2013).
Soil	The suitability of a country's soil for agricultural production. Michalopoulos and Papaioannou (2013).

Formal Institutions

Liberal democracy	Measures the extent to which a country upholds liberal democratic principles, including electoral democracy, the rule of law, individual liberties, and checks on executive power. Measured in 2019. Data are collected from V-dem version 13 (Coppedge et al. 2023). In log form.
Economic freedom	Economic freedom index measures the level of economic freedom based on five categories: size of government, monetary policy and price stability, legal structure and security of private ownership, freedom to trade with foreigners, and regulation of credit, labor, and business. The index ranges from zero to ten, with ten representing a greater degree of freedom. The index is not adjusted for

Rule of law	gender disparity. Measured in 2019. Data are collected from Gwartney et al. (2024) and are in log form. Rule of Law captures perceptions of the extent to which agents have confidence in and abide by the rules of society, and in particular the quality of contract enforcement, property rights, the police, and the courts, as well as the likelihood of crime and violence. Measured in 2019. Collected from Worldwide Governance Indicators (2021). Data are standardized.
Control corruption	Control of corruption captures perceptions of the extent to which public power is exercised for private gain, including both petty and grand forms of corruption, as well as "capture" of the state by elites and private interests. Measured in 2019. Collected from Worldwide Governance Indicators (2021). Data are standardized.
WBL index	Women Business and the Law (WBL) index measures legal differences between men's and women's access to economic opportunities. Calculated by taking the average of eight areas: mobility, workplace, pay, marriage, parenthood, entrepreneurship, assets, and pension. Scored 0-100 with 100 representing equal economic rights for women. Data are measured in 2019, collected from World Bank (2024), and are in log form.
WPR index	Women's political rights include the right to vote, right to run for political office, right to hold elected and appointed government positions, right to join political parties, and the right to petition government officials. Collected from CIRI Human Rights Dataset. Measured in 2011. Data are in log form.

Instruments

Historical disease	The number of nine infectious diseases historically prevalent in a country. Fincher et al. (2008).
Rainfall variation	The natural log of the coefficient of intertemporal variation of monthly rainfall from 1900 to 2009. Davis (2016).
Pronoun drop	The share of a country's population speaking a language in which the expression of nominal pronouns is not required. From Davis and Abdurazokzoda (2016).
LIFE	Labor intensity of traditional agriculture is measured using a Labor Intensity of Farming Estimate (LIFE). This measure is designed to capture the labor requirements of different crops based on their historical cultivation practices. Collected from Ang (2019).

Appendix C: Country list, n=93

Albania	Germany	Pakistan
Algeria	Ghana	Peru
Argentina	Greece	Philippines
Armenia	Guatamala	Poland
Australia	Haiti	Puerto Rico
Austria	Hong Kong	Qatar
Azerbaijan	Hungary	Russia
Bangladesh	Iceland	Rwanda
Belarus	India	Saudi Arabia
Bolivia	Indonesia	Singapore
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Iran	Slovakia
Brazil	Iraq	Slovenia
Bulgaria	Italy	South Africa
Burkina Faso	Japan	South Korea
Canada	Jordan	Spain
Chile	Kazakhstan	Sweden
China	Kyrgystan	Switzerland
Colombia	Latvia	Tanzania
Croatia	Lebanon	Thailand
Cyprus	Libya	Trinidad and Tobago
Czech Republic	Lithuania	Tunisia
Denmark	Macedonia	Turkey
Dominican Republic	Malaysia	Uganda
Ecuador	Mali	Ukraine
Egypt	Mexico	United Kingdom
El Salvador	Moldova	United State of America
Estonia	Morocco	Uruguay
Ethiopia	Netherlands	Uzbekistan
Finland	New Zealand	Vietnam
France	Nigeria	Zambia
Georgia	Norway	Zimbabwe

Appendix D: Individualism and patriarchal attitudes, instrumental variable analysis, first stage

Dep. variable:	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
	Indv	Hof Indv	Indv	Indv	Indv	Indv	Indv	Indv	Indv	Indv
Historical disease	-0.85*** (0.19)	-0.35 (0.21)	-0.85*** (0.19)	-0.85*** (0.19)	-0.66** (0.21)	-0.79*** (0.14)	-0.58*** (0.17)	-0.80*** (0.17)	-0.80*** (0.20)	-0.77*** (0.21)
Ancestral rainfall variation	-0.70*** (0.20)	-0.39 (0.33)	-0.70*** (0.20)	-0.70*** (0.20)	-0.55** (0.24)	-0.44** (0.18)	-0.10 (0.18)	-0.48** (0.21)	-0.62** (0.19)	-0.93** (0.31)
Pronoun drop					-0.56** (0.27)					
LIFE					0.08 (0.10)					
Trust						3.48*** (0.52)				
Religious Affiliations							yes			
Religious attendance								0.30*** (0.06)		
Plough									-0.07 (0.19)	
Agricultural revolution									-0.05 (0.04)	
Climate										-0.39 (0.49)
Soil										-0.68 (0.70)
Constant	-0.23 (0.21)	-1.41*** (0.24)	-0.23 (0.21)	-0.23 (0.21)	-0.48 (0.96)	-0.52** (0.19)	-0.10 (0.39)	-1.05*** (0.27)	-0.05 (0.25)	0.51 (0.41)
# observations	83	61	83	83	73	83	83	83	83	75

Notes: Presented in this table are first stage estimations for the second stage results presented in Table 3, Panel A. Detailed variable descriptions are provided in Appendix B. All specifications include controls for share of oil rents, absolute value of latitude, a landlocked dummy variable, and common law. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. ***, **, and * denote significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively.

Appendix E: Individualism, institutions, and patriarchal attitudes

Dep. variable: PAI	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Individualism	-0.67*** (0.07)	-0.75*** (0.07)	-0.87*** (0.09)	-0.79*** (0.09)	-0.61*** (0.06)	-0.72*** (0.07)
Liberal democracy	-0.27** (0.09)					
Economic freedom		-0.04 (0.68)				
Rule of law			0.14 (0.10)			
Control corruption				0.02 (0.09)		
WBL index					-1.62*** (0.31)	
WPR index						-0.57** (0.22)
Constant	-0.70** (0.23)	-0.39 (1.37)	-0.49** (0.21)	-0.52** (0.21)	6.52*** (1.39)	-0.05 (0.31)
# observations	92	91	93	93	93	90
Adjusted R ²	0.71	0.68	0.69	0.68	0.77	0.70

Notes: Detailed variable descriptions are provided in Appendix B. All specifications include controls for share of oil rents, absolute value of latitude, a landlocked dummy variable, and common law. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses. ***, **, and * denote significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively.